

VII International Forum on Teacher Education

Individual Approach as a Basis for Language Teachers' Competence in Research Activities

Alla M. Antipova* (a), Elena G. Chernysheva (b), Victor F. Chertov (c)

(a), (b), (c) Moscow Pedagogical State University,
119991, Moscow (Russia), M. Pirogovskaya street, 1h, 1b, e-mail: mail@mpgu.edu

Abstract

The article is devoted to the implementation of the principle of individualization with the purpose of generating promptitude for research and development in future teachers-philologists. The article analyzes the experience of conducting research work in higher education institutions, substantiates the model of training a teacher-researcher, determines the conditions for applying the principle of individualization at different levels of education (bachelor's, master's, postgraduate degrees). The main research methods are the methods of tier/structural and content analysis, projective and ascertaining modeling, and the comparative typological method. The methodological instruments include the analysis of scientific literature, pedagogical experience, questioning of students, and interviewing teachers. Special attention is paid to the experience of individualization of research work at the Institute of Philology of Moscow Pedagogical State University. The authors analyze organizational and pedagogical prerequisites for the implementation of the principle of individualization in order to generate promptitude in students and postgraduates to research and development work; the following conditions for its effective application have been determined: reliance on the traditions and modern areas of activity of scientific schools that have been developed at the academic departments, involvement of students in an active search for scientific discussion platforms, more active testing of the research activities results, taking into account the personal vector of value attitudes and young researchers' compliance with the conventionality of the scientific ethos. The results of the study can be used in the higher pedagogical education for the purpose of organizing research work of students and in expert evaluation of educational programs.

Keywords: pedagogical education, teacher-researcher, research activity, individual approach.

© 2021 Alla M. Antipova, Elena G. Chernysheva, Victor F. Chertov

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2021 (VII International Forum on Teacher Education)

* Corresponding author. E-mail: antipovaalla@mail.ru

Introduction

Current strategic priorities of the educational system in Russia imply establishing new competence models for students at pedagogical universities for their research activities, considered as a pedagogical process mainly aimed at the development of each student's personality. At the same time, the personality development should directly correlate with the general value mindset representing scientific knowledge as the most important cultural meaning and a fundamental factor in human interaction with the world.

The issue of implementing the individual approach principle in training future teachers for performing research activities is becoming especially relevant in modern conditions. It is important to note that the individual approach in education is seen as one of the strategic directions of the development of Russian education (Baidikova, 2016), which is proved by the regulatory documents. Thus, the Federal Law of the Russian Federation on Education introduced the term of Individual Curriculum (article 2, paragraph 23). Such terms as the Individual Educational Route and Individual Educational Trajectory, which are interpreted in different ways by modern researchers, are widely used in the theory and practice of education (Khutorskoy, 2003; Berezhnaya, 2012). The authors of this article share the point of view of Grebennikova and Ignatovich, according to whom the individual educational route of a student is "his or her own project of advancement in the educational space, developed jointly with a teacher and recorded in the form of an individual educational program," which results in the individual educational trajectory (2013, p. 531).

While determining the content of the individual approach principle for the process of gaining research competence, it is pointed out by researchers that compliance with the said principle becomes, on the one hand, the response to "the demand of society for the individual training of a researcher in conditions of mass education", and on the other hand, "the requirement for consideration of individual abilities, including the ones of gifted students." The correlation of "the defined tasks with the life experience and capabilities of students (doctoral students)" is of equal importance (21st Century Researcher, 2018, pp. 40-41).

The inclusion of Russian universities in the Bologna Process and the introduction of three levels of higher education (bachelor's, master's, doctorate degree) led to the introduction of new tasks, including those related to the determination of the content, stages of training and indicators of achievement of the relevant competence in the field of research activities at different levels of education, taking into account the principle of continuity.

The process of training a teacher-researcher is based on combining traditions and modern trends in the activities of scientific schools that have been developed at university departments that take part in the implementation of educational programs for bachelor's, master's and doctorate degrees.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The research aim is as follows: analysis of the practice of implementing the individual approach as a basis for students' competence in research activities at Pedagogical Education course of the bachelor's programs (department of Russian Language and Literature), master's programs (courses related to philological education) and programs for doctorate degrees (Theory and methods of teaching and training (Russian), Theory and methods of teaching and training (literature)); determination of the importance of a scalable model of implementation of the above approach in higher education.

The objectives of the study are related to the identification of conditions for the effective application of the individual approach principle in training students for performing research activities, depending on the level of education: bachelor's, master's, doctorate degrees.

Literature review

The research work of students is focused on mastering the methodology of research activities by future experts, deepening their scientific knowledge, and developing their creative independence. An equally important objective is the training of a creatively thinking teacher that follows the principles of the scientific arrangement of his or her work, cognitive — retrospective and prospective — reflection in personal and professional development, analytical and synthetic skills in relation to the subject research gap, the ability to resolve problem situations (Matyushkin, 2017). Based on the analysis of modern researchers' articles, official documents and practice in arranging students' research work in Russian and foreign higher education institutions, including Moscow State Pedagogical University, there could be drawn a conclusion of an obvious popularity of the issues related to the formation and development of teachers' research competence (Barkhatova, Lomasko, & Pak, 2019; Chertov, Antipova, & Zhuravlev, 2019; Yamaguchi & Hall, 2017), attention to the methodology and methods of students' scientific research (Afanasyev, Gribkova, & Ukolova, 2020; Mokiy & Lukyanova, 2020; Harland, 2011; Robson, 2016) and joint research activities of teachers and students (co-authorship as a form of scientific cooperation) (Gehlbach, Brinkworth, & Harris, 2012; Payne & Monk-Turner, 2005; Northwest Nazarene University, 2017), as well as the relevance of considering the implementation of the individual approach as a basis for teachers' competence in research activities (Demchenko, 2013; Karavaeva, 2018; Antipova, 2019; Antipova, 2020; Getmanskaya, 2020).

At the same time, it should be noted that most scientific publications cover either the general principles of the organization of research activities by students and postgraduates, or certain organizational aspects. The problem of individualization is also considered mainly in connection with the definition of the individual educational route, the assessment of the level of students' promptitude to research and development and its effectiveness, that is, most publications directly address the same issues of work organization, and do not cover promising areas, methodological approaches, the problems of scientific research corresponding to the areas of activity of scientific schools, the tasks of training and the competences generated at each education stage (bachelor's, master's, postgraduate programs).

The training for performing research activities is a long-term process. The competence in research activities is interpreted as "personal education that determines the state of the personal development and includes a motivational and high-value attitude to such activities, a system of methodological knowledge, research skills that allow to use them in the most efficient way in solving emerging professional and pedagogical problems" (Shadchin, 2012, p. 171).

The training of students includes research activities within the educational process, and research activities that complement the educational process (Balashov, 2002). The higher education in general has accumulated significant experience in arranging research work, the theoretically substantiated approaches and criteria for assessing its results, and also has identified a range of relevant issues that require additional research:

- development of a model of training students for performing research activities (including students of pedagogical universities);
- implementation of the individual approach principle in training students for performing research activities within bachelor's, master's, doctorate programs in the current educational practice of Russian universities;
- continuity in the implementation of the objectives for gaining research competence by students at different levels of higher education (bachelor's, master's, doctorate degrees);
- development of the high-value attitude of junior students to research activities.

Methodology

The methodological basis of this research is made up of studying works in the field of higher education pedagogy, methodology and methods of students' research work. The basic research methods used are the analysis of scientific literature, the study of official documents, pedagogical experience.

The scientific sources selected for the analysis are based on the criteria of representativeness (representation of different university traditions and scientific schools), scientific and ethical correctness, relevance (citation), multidisciplinary character, complexity (a combination of theoretical understanding, practical development and experimental verification of the proposed approaches, strategies, and technologies). Special attention was paid to the publications proposing specific areas of work that contribute to the effective implementation of the individualization principle in the process of research work performed by students. Additional sources in the form of materials posted on the official websites of Russian and foreign universities: programs of training courses, scientific forums, associations, societies (approximately 100 files).

Among the applied specific research methods, the main attention has been given to the comparative typological study of the implemented forms of students' research work and the content of the current educational programs of different universities concerning the possible introduction of the individual approach in gaining research competence. The development of applicable models for implementing the individual approach in the above-mentioned subject field involves the method of level/structural analysis and model development.

The empirical study was conducted at the Institute of Philology of the Moscow Pedagogical State University on a voluntary basis. The informed consent was gained from students and postgraduates. Members of the student scientific society doing the bachelor's and master's degree courses, and participants of the School for Young Scientists participated in the survey. The respondents were asked in order to determine the field of their scientific interests; identify school experience of participation in scientific circles / societies / conferences / seminars; identify the motives for joining the student scientific society and expected results; determine specific types of activities, the regularity of their implementation, personal achievements in the field of research and development, difficulties in its implementation; analysis of specific proposals for improving the work of the student scientific society and the organization of research work of students.

There was also an interview with the heads of the students' research work at the Institute of Philology, who gave their consent to the video recording and the use of the materials for further analysis. In the course of the interview the authors set out to determine the most important conditions for applying the principle of individualization during the formation of research competencies in students; identify difficulties in implementing the individual approach to the organization of research work; identify illustrative examples from the experience of applying the principle of individualization.

Results

The analysis of scientific literature (Shadchin, 2012; Yarkova, 2013; Barkhatova et al., 2019) and work experience of Russian and foreign universities, and personal experience of the authors enables for setting a model of training a teacher-researcher at different levels of education (bachelor's, master's, doctorate degrees). The model includes the following components:

- 1) evaluation of the students' competence level in research work (the level of development of necessary skills), identification of gifted students (diagnostic component);
- 2) identification of motivation for research work (motivational component);
- 3) the knowledge necessary for choosing the research topic, setting and solving research problems, choosing research methods (cognitive component);
- 4) the skills and abilities related to research activities (activity component);
- 5) self-assessment and introspection of students' own research activities, determination of ways of self-development in research knowledge (reflexive component).

At different levels of education, in the implementation of the individual approach principle, the indicated components will have their own specific application. At each subsequent level of education from a bachelor's degree to a master's degree to a doctorate degree:

- 1) the material, problems, research directions shall become more complex;
- 2) the research thesaurus shall expand;
- 3) the research methodology (combination of different methods, approaches and others) shall become more varied.

The study and generalization of the pedagogical experience of teachers at the Institute of Philology of Moscow Pedagogical State University makes it possible to determine the most effective organizational and pedagogical conditions in order to apply the principle of individualization and to generate readiness for research activities in philology students and graduate students during the process of their methodical training.

Throughout their studies, students enrolled in bachelor's programs (Techer Education Course) perform research work within the educational process: preparation of annotations, essays, speeches and reports at university lessons; preparation of educational research papers, term papers (Years 2-4), performing research assignments during teaching practice (Years 3-5). The research activity presented as a fragment of general cognitive research work when writing essays, term papers, appears to a large extent as a self-sufficient and holistic process, purposefully carried out stage-by-stage when writing the graduation thesis (Year 5). The internal logic of this process corresponds to the phases of the cognitive/epistemological individual development in the process of performing research work.

When mastering methodological subjects (Methods of Teaching the Russian Language, Methods of Teaching Literature and others), students present the theoretical material related to specific issues, comparing different points of view on the way to solving key methodological problems, they are trained in performing communication tasks (imitation of teaching practice) with a clearly expressed focus on gaining up-to-date linguistic/literary, as well as psychological and pedagogical knowledge, and application of different types of students' research activities: writing reports with preparation of the text presentation, as well as preparatory materials and abstracts, performing abstract reviews of scientific journals (Literature at School, Russian Language at School, Russian Literature, Philological Class, Pedagogical Studies and many others), specific theoretical reports on one or two significant sources, detailed opposition based on reports, essays. The methodological courses integrate the theoretical material learned by the student in a number of subjects: Pedagogical Studies, Psychology, Physiology, linguistic and literary subjects, specific methods, etc. This contributes to the development of systematic thinking, which is the most important indicator of the professional culture of a modern teacher.

The emphasis on the individual approach to the arrangement of students' activities implies the developments of a more complex independent individual work, introduced at lessons of methodological courses. When performing all types of practices, writing term papers, students perform individual tasks (solve various issues), the topics of which may include the history of language/literary education – an important direction of research activities of university departments related to methods of teaching. Studying of the methodology history as a part of the bachelor's work implies mainly the analysis of positive experience, the study of the methodological heritage of renowned teachers, educational and methodological literature, discussion materials on the issues of school studying of the Russian language and literature, gaining the up-to-date knowledge on methodological ideas in modern educational practice (for example, Methodical Heritage of Baltalon, the Interconnection of Class and Extracurricular Reading in the Study of Literary Tales).

Historical reviews prepared by students on the basis of studying available sources become the beginning of their more serious research in the field of the history of philological education and methodological science later at the master's and doctorate courses.

Experts rightly point out that the master's degree, in comparison with the bachelor's degree, provides more opportunities for developing individual educational routes for students. Considering the master's degree as a level of higher pedagogical education, there should be highlighted the deeper academic training and focus on the competence of a teacher-researcher.

The Institute of Philology implements master's programs of Pedagogical Education Course with the focus on philological education: Contemporary Strategies in Philological Education, Pedagogical Engineering in Philological Education. The programs can be characterized as follows:

- firstly, the programs are cross-subject, directly leading to cooperation between different scientific schools and areas of research;
- secondly, the programs are predominantly of an applied nature, setting only practical tasks for gaining the research competence necessary for a teacher, an advocate of science;
- thirdly, the programs imply the use of available printed sources and the widespread use of digital resources, modern means of presenting scientific information.

In the process of mastering all the subjects within the educational program, the skills of working with educational and scientific texts get constantly improved: questioning and analyzing the content of the text; preparation of annotations; preparation of text-based theses; preparation of synopses; comparative analysis of journal articles, textbooks; preparation of abstracts (abstract-synopsis, abstract-resume, abstract-review, abstract-report); commenting on a scientific text (by applying the method of taking "notes in the margins"); peer review (possible analysis of ready-made reviews, comparing the plan of another person's review with the plan of your own review); answering key questions; drawing up a plan for the content of the text; drawing up supporting logic diagrams, mind maps, tables; mastering the use of references as bibliographic material (systematization of sources: bibliographic list, annotated list). Working with reference publications might also include compiling a terminological dictionary on the topic (area or research); comparison of definitions of the basic categories of the methodology in various dictionaries according to particular methods; analytical review of dictionary entries; preparation of a dictionary entry, for example, for a biobibliographical dictionary (Chertov, 2018); compiling a glossary; a thesaurus.

An important role is given to the tasks involving online sources: search for and processing of information (abstract-review, analysis of existing abstracts on this topic published online, their evaluation); training in arranging online conferences. The tasks for the presentation of works online are considered to be relevant as well: publication of thematic web pages, a collection of the author's works. At the same time, the tasks may be aimed at applying innovative science-based cognitive models: content analysis, gestalt monitoring, retrospective and prospective reflection, identification of internal epistemological contradictions, possible logical antinomies and aporias, analysis of the center and periphery of knowledge components of the text of a textbook.

At the master's level, the studying targets of students' independent research are significantly expanded, with proposing topics that lead to the study of rare or unpublished (archival) materials, a comparative analysis of different areas and approaches in the methodology of teaching the Russian language and literature (in Russian and foreign secondary and higher education), detailed coverage of history of individual teaching methods, forms of class and extracurricular activities, for example, School Reading Club as a Form of Introduction to Fiction, the Issue of Educating a Creative Reader in the History of Methodological Science and Modern Research, School Theatre: History of Formation and Stages of Development.

The studying targets of research work of master's students, closely connected to the areas of scientific research of methodology departments, also include a comparative analysis of various educational systems and technologies, including those that have become widespread in a foreign scientific school, the study of the best practices of modern language teachers. The most important link in the research activities of master's students is the identification of the genesis and the determination of a broad context of the studied object in the social and cultural, as well as scientific and epistemological areas. Nowadays master's students represent a considerable pool of potential doctoral students applying for Education and Pedagogical Sciences Course or Linguistics and Literary Studies Course, where the fundamental and narrow-focused research returns to being the center of the educational agenda at the third level of higher education.

At the doctorate level, the topics of scientific research are significantly expanded, although their main areas are basically the same.

There are introduced the topics related to the analysis of separate periods in the history of literary education, trends, pedagogical phenomena (Schoolchildren Independent Work Issues in Literature in the Works of Methodologists of the Late 19th – Early 20th Centuries; Literary Conversations in the Russian School of the 19th – Early 20th Centuries as a Pedagogical Phenomenon and others), topics related to reading, analysis and interpretation of literary works, the use of modern teaching technologies, are applied at a large scale.

In the course of preparing the graduation thesis (bachelor's theses, master's theses) and research works, students fully master different research methods: theoretical (comparative historical analysis, application of structural typology, multilevel and multi-scale modeling) and empirical (method of pedagogical observations, questionnaires, interviews, rating, self-assessment, conversation, method of diagnostic tests, pedagogical experiment, experimental work, generalization of pedagogical experience).

The growing influence of mass culture, multimedia forms of presentation of individual and joint achievements can lead (and is already leading) to changes in the scientific discourse itself. The syncretism from the field of arts is transmitted to the field of scientific knowledge, at least in its representation. The format of modern articles sets, in addition to the really necessary points, certain clichés that do not allow the author's individuality to be fully expressed. In the case of young researchers, there becomes evident the following of a template, copying, uncritical use of someone else's text and sources that other authors have referred to. There appear very peculiar examples when articles contain distorted references to the sources making it clear that the authors of the articles have not studied the sources themselves and have no idea who they are citing, men or women, Doctors of Philosophy or students retelling someone else's thoughts, presenting other people's ideas. The individual approach is directly related to the student's personal attitude to the cited material, methodology, to the idea of anthropocentricity of the scientific process, not impersonal, but having in its course vivid biographies, compliance with the scientific ethos, which is understood as "an affectively colored complex of values and standards that are considered to be obligatory for a true scientist" (Merton, 2006, p. 769). Among the scientific ethical standards, the most relevant are the service to science, awareness of personal responsibility for the results and outcomes of the scientific research.

The individual needs and individual psychological characteristics of undergraduate and postgraduate students of the Institute of Philology of MPGU are taken into account as fully as possible when implementing various forms of research work that complements the educational process (when choosing the topic, setting goals/objectives, selecting research methods). Students have the opportunity to choose the form of their participation.

First of all, that means membership in the student research circle, work at a seminar of the research group for the study of the heritage of Losev (at the Losev Center for the Russian Language and Culture) and/or the School for Young Scientists.

According to the survey of members of the student scientific society and participants of the School for Young Scientists, their scientific interests are connected both with the study of the work of individual writers, and issues related to mythopoetics, extensive ties of literature with philosophy, and various types of art (especially cinema and syncretic arts). The majority of respondents noted that they had no school experience of participating in scientific circles / societies / conferences / seminars. Of particular interest to the researchers were the answers to the question about what prompted students to enter the student scientific society. The most popular (and expected) answers were the following: being interested in philological science (the subject of the study), and the desire to find self-fulfillment. Some responses pointed out to the influence of certain teachers. When answering the question about what you get from the membership in a scientific society, it was mainly about the possibility of having interesting communication, self-development, getting new knowledge, participation in scientific conferences, seminars and in the process of organizing them. Among the specific activities that members of the scientific society are involved in are: participation in conferences, seminars, meetings with famous scientists; writing articles; making reports; and participation in discussions. The members of the student scientific society named some difficulties they were facing with when performing research and development work. Most often they mentioned the lack of free time. In addition, students admitted to having the white sheet syndrome and lack of knowledge about the technology of writing a scientific article. According to the students, scientific supervisors help to overcome certain difficulties by outlining “specific ways in the development of a particular topic or problem”. Some mentioned “self-discipline”, “moral and volitional training”. Proposals for improving the work of the student scientific society and the organization of research work in general were related to holding an interdisciplinary annual student conference, attracting graduate students to work, and expanding contacts with other universities.

Future language teachers, under the guidance of university teachers, make up their own research route. Interviewing scientists of the Institute of Philology allowed us to determine important conditions for applying the principle of individualization: familiarization with the traditions of scientific schools of Moscow Pedagogical State University; a wide range of possible areas of research activity (Russian and foreign literature; world literature about children and for children; synthesis of arts in the global art culture, problems of childhood reading), well-managed organization of research and development work of students; ongoing participation in scientific conferences.

The main difficulties in implementing the individual approach to the organization of research work of students were attributed to the search/selection of a subject that, on the one hand, would be in line with the fields of a particular scientific school, would be relevant, had novelty, and on the other hand, would be of interest to the student and outlined possible vectors of his/her development. By suggesting the ways to improve the organization of research and development work of students, the leaders highlighted the importance of ongoing work in social media. The systematic supervision by the leading scientists of the Institute of Philology, the individually set (including tutoring, taking into account the value attitude of participants) working format with the aim of increasing motivation of the participants and improving their competence in setting the relevant objectives are the most important components of the individual approach principle in training students' competence in research activities.

Participation in the School for Young Scientists and youth conferences of prominent Russian scientists, representatives of academic institutions, leading philological schools of Moscow Pedagogical State University and other universities lead the process of applying the individual approach to gaining research competence to a high cross-institutional level. For example, the Corresponding Member of the Russian Academy of Sciences Toporkov has given a number of master classes at scientific conferences and meetings of the school, providing targeted comments on the speeches of young researchers and giving them focused expert recommendations. As a result of such work, individual research projects get integrated into academic science.

The research work of students enrolled in bachelor's and master's programs within Pedagogical Education Course has a vivid professional and pedagogical focus, contributes to the development of the individuality of future teachers, the mastering of skills in scientific research and the arrangement of experimental work in the field of science and philological education. The research work of doctoral students (Education and Pedagogical Sciences Course) is an integral part of the training system for a highly qualified teacher of higher education and a researcher capable of combining teaching and research activities in the chosen field.

Discussion

A comparison of the results of the conducted study with the results of studies performed by other authors showed that insufficient attention is paid to the development of implementation models of the principle of individualization in the generation of students' promptitude for research and development activities. This problem is rarely considered in the context of development of scientific schools and fields, and their interaction. Western researchers, as a rule, do not go beyond the forms of cooperation.

In the works of Russian specialists, the conditions of effective research activity include the presence in a higher education institution of authoritative research teams, scientific schools and their leading scientists in certain fields of knowledge (Bogoslovsky, 2000; Yarkova, 2013), regardless of the process of preparing future teachers-philologists for research and development. Even in the works devoted to the formation of research competence in philologists during the pedagogical activity (Churaeva, 2013), there is not enough information on scientific schools and strategic directions in the field of philological education, which, from our point of view, are determinative of the search directions for young scientists.

The analysis of the organizational and methodological conditions for the implementation of the individual approach principle in training students of bachelor's, master's and doctorate programs for gaining competence in research activities allows to identify a number of problems and develop recommendations for the formation of a system for modeling an individual educational trajectory that ensures reaching the competence in research activities.

The identified problems are as follows:

- insufficient development of the conditions for the competitive selection of talented youth and diagnostic tools for determining the competence of students in research activities / identifying gifted students for doing research work;
- the constant increase in the teaching load, which negatively affects the results of the research work, as well as the supervision over the research work of students;
- the small proportion of real projects and assignments for term papers and graduation theses, especially those related to setting the necessary aim for the targeted use of the results of the research work in the practice of schools, universities, the system of additional education;
- the lack of infrastructural interactions in the field of research and scientific practice of undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral students (not enough demonstration of scientific achievements in social and pedagogical institutions, almost complete absence of PR technologies, poor representation in information environments);
- non-systemic interaction of Russian students with foreign students within the institute/university, the lack of consideration of national scientific traditions when working with foreign students.

Below there are highlighted the directions of work on the formation of elements of the system for modeling an individual educational trajectory, which ensures reaching the competence in research activities:

- close connection of research work with the educational process, development and testing of elective/optional courses and/or programs of additional education on the basics of research activities; expanding the range of elective courses, within which students could receive information on the current results of the research work of teachers/departments;
- amendments to local regulations, in particular to the regulation for calculating the teaching load; encouragement means for efficient research work and its supervision, as well as development of educational and methodological works for students on research work issues;
- planning of systematic interconnections between departments in the implementation of research activities of students: study of the experience of working with gifted students and its presentation; taking into account cross-subject advantages as the most important modus and factor of the research work efficiency of undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral students; conducting cross-department scientific conferences and creating temporary or permanent research groups analyzing the topics of research work in the field of philological education, its methodology, scientific novelty, theoretical and practical significance, promising areas and efficient research methods;
- establishment of a close relationship between the university and educational and scientific organizations as bases (sites) for conducting experimental work;
- implementation of a stable system of support and encouragement for students that successfully perform their research work;
- development of infrastructural interactions in the field of student research and scientific practice: publication of detailed information on the scientific schools of the departments in online sources or on the university website; regular updating of information on departments, their teaching staff, personal pages of teachers, the list of their scientific publications on the university website; regular face-to-face presentations of scientific schools of departments, brief publications on the results of scientific activities of departments (holding conferences, publishing scientific articles and monographs, defending theses at dissertation councils, information on the development of department scientific projects) on the website and in social networks (for each student group); holding open meetings with reports of professors of departments with the invitation of undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral students, including scientific sessions;
- establishing productive interaction of Russian undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral students with foreign students, possible updating/consideration of national scientific traditions when working with foreign students.

The research outcomes have revealed some obvious tendencies in the system of arranging students' research activities, the choice of topics and research methods, as well as forms of presentation of their results:

- on the one hand, a decrease in the cultural level, the level of understanding the historical development of linguistic, literary, cultural and scientific processes, and on the other hand, the distinct need of the students themselves to raise the level of their philological culture, the quality of their training;
- interconnections of various subjects as the most important modus and factor of students' research work efficiency;
- syncretism of the research object and subject, as well as the applied methods (a consistent combination of various scientific methods);
- some leveling of value attitudes and scientific intentions when adapting a student to the requirements of a scientific school; deviations from the ethos of science, partial or sometimes radical disregard of the historical approach in science, the frequent omission of historical development, substitution of causal connections by associative ones;
- replacement of causal links by associative ones, co-presence of explicit or hidden antinomies in the text.

The possible solutions for minimizing risks are seen as follows:

- analysis of the topics of educational and research works (individual research assignments, term papers, graduation theses and research works) presented by departments, and their subsequent adjustment with consideration of the indicated trends;
- preparation and holding of scientific/methodological seminars on the scientific organization of work, methodological basis and research methods, technologies for writing a scientific article, etc.;
- study of research areas of scientific schools of departments/university, more active use of foreign sources, comparative analysis of national and foreign studies on the selected scientific topic.

Conclusion

Studying the practice of applying the individual approach in students' research work (within the educational process and complementing it) in terms of content, practical results, functioning shows the possibility to consider the individual approach as a process of a person-to-person relationship correlated with hermeneutic ideas rooted in humanities of today.

The substantiation of the actualization model of the individualization principle when generating promptitude in future teachers-philologists to research and development is based on a multidimensional analysis of scientific literature in the field of methodology and methods of organizing research work in a pedagogical university and the study of teaching experience.

Important conditions for the application of this principle have been identified: reliance on the traditions and modern areas of activity of scientific schools, involving them in an active search for scientific discussion platforms, "condensing" of the very space of such discussions, more active approbation while taking into account the personal vector of value attitudes and the compliance of young researchers with the ethos of science.

The main value of the research outcomes is their possible use in the examination and subsequent adjustment of curricula, educational programs, assessment tools on the basis of a more consistent implementation of the individual approach, the principles of continuity, consistency and the systematic approach in development of teachers' research competence.

Funding

This research has been performed as part of the implementation of the state assignment of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation – *Peculiarities of the Implementation of the Individual Approach Principle in Training for Competence in Research Activities* (2020).

Competing interests

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Acknowledgements

The authors have no support to report.

References

- Afanasyev, V. V., Gribkova, O. V., & Ukolova, L. I. (2020). *Research methods and methodology*. Moscow: Yurayt.
- Antipova, A. M. (Ed.). (2019). *Master's Degree for Science and Education: Relevant Issues of Modern Literary Education: Materials of the 5th Russian National Scientific Videoconference with International Guests*. Moscow: MPGU.
- Antipova, A. M. (Ed.). (2020). *Master's Degree for Science and Education: Relevant Issues of Modern Literary Education: Materials of the 6th International Scientific Videoconference*. Moscow: MPGU.
- Baidikova, N. L. (2016). Individualization of post-graduate education using credit assessment system. *International Research Journal*, 53(11) Part 3, 9-12. doi: 10.18454/IRJ.2016.53.096
- Balashov, V. V. (Ed.). (2002). Arrangement of students' research activities at Russian universities. *Main prerequisites for the arrangement and development of students' research activities at universities* (2nd ed., Vol. 1). Moscow: Gos. un-t. upr.
- Barkhatova, D. A., Lomasko, P. S., & Pak, N. I. (2019). A model of readiness for research activity of students of pedagogical high school and teachers of educational institutions. *Open Education*, 23(3), 4-13. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21686/1818-4243-2019-3-4-13>
- Berezhnaya, I. F. (2012). Pedagogical projecting of professional development of future specialists' individual trajectory in the university educational process: Theoretical and methodological aspect. *Global Scientific Potential*, 11(2), 27-31.
- Bogoslovsky, V. I. (2000). *Scientific support of the educational process at a pedagogical university: methodological characteristics*. St. Petersburg: Publishing house of RSPU.
- Chertov, V. F. (Ed.). (2018). *The Methodology of Teaching Literature. Personalities: Bibliographic Dictionary*. Moscow: MPGU.
- Chertov, V. F., Antipova, A. M., & Zhuravlev, V. P. (2019). Literary Education History as a Research Object at a Pedagogical University. In S. V. Ivanova (Ed.), *Educational Space in the Information Age (EEIA-2019)* (pp. 789-800). Moscow: ISRO RAO.
- Churaeva, E.P. (2013). Research and development competence of a philologist in pedagogical activity. *Vector of Science of Togliatti State University*, 26(4), 300-303.

- Demchenko, Z. A. (2013). *Students' research activities at higher educational institutions in Russia (1950–2000s): Historical background, concepts, approaches*. Arkhangelsk: IPCz SAFU.
- Gehlbach, H., Brinkworth, M. E., & Harris, A. D. (2012). Changes in teacher-student relationships. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(4), 690-704. doi:10.1111/j.2044-8279.2011.02058.x
- Getmanskaya, E. V. (Ed.). (2020). *21st Century Teacher: Proceedings of the 5th Students' Scientific and Practical Conference*. Moscow: Buki Vedi.
- Grebennikova, V. M., & Ignatovich, S. S. (2013). Designing the individual educational route as joint activity student and teacher. *Fundamental Research*, 11-3, 529-534.
- Harland, D. J. (2011). *STEM. Student Research Handbook*. Arlington, VA.: National Science Teachers Association.
- Karavaeva, E. V. (Ed.). (2018). *21st Century Researcher: Competence Development in the System of Higher Education*. Moscow: Geoinfo.
- Khutorskoy, A. V. (2003). *Didactic Heuristics: Theory and technology of creative learning*. Moscow: Izd-vo MGU.
- Matyushkin, A. M. (2017). *Psychology of thinking. Thinking as a solution to problem situations*. Moscow: Mezhdunarodnyye otnosheniya.
- Merton, R. (2006). *Social Theory and Social Structure*. (E.N. Egorova, Trans.). Moscow: AST: Khranitel.
- Mokiy, V. S., & Lukyanova, T. A. (2020). *Research Methodology. Cross-subject Approaches and Methods*. Moscow: Yurayt.
- Northwest Nazarene University (2017). *Professor and Student co-author academic article*. Retrieved from <https://www.nnu.edu/news/professor-and-student-co-author-academic-article>
- Payne, B. K., & Monk-Turner, E. (2005). *Benefits of writing with students*. Retrieved from <http://rapidintellect.com/AEQweb/6jan295415.htm>
- Robson, C. (2016). *How to do a research project: A guide for undergraduate students*. (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.

- Shadchin, I. V. (2012). Methods for assessing the level of competence of university students in research activities. In *Issues and Prospects of Education Development: Materials of the 2nd International Scientific Conference*. (pp. 170-173). Perm: Mercury. Retrieved from <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/58/2276/>
- Yamaguchi, R., & Hall, A. (2017). *A Compendium of Education Technology Research Funded by NCER and NCSE: 2002–2014 (NCER 2017–0001)*. Washington, DC: National Center for Education Research, Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education. Retrieved from <https://ies.ed.gov/ncer/pubs/20170001/pdf/20170001.pdf>
- Yarkova, T. A. (2013). Scientific bases of the students' research activity organization in higher pedagogical institutions. *The Herald of Chelyabinsk State Pedagogical University*, 3, 215-228.